

The Impact of the Buntukunik Airport Development Project on the Economic Development of Residents Around the Airport

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the economic impact of the community around the airport on the Buntu Kunik Airport development project after the airport development project, to determine the impact of labor conditions on the community around the Buntu Kunik Airport after the airport development project and the third to determine the impact of tourism conditions around the Buntu Kunik Airport after development. In this study, researchers used qualitative research to be able to understand phenomena in a natural social context that describes social problems in a person from a behavioral point of view. The sample selected in this study amounted to 20 people. The data used for this study include primary data and secondary data. The analysis method used in this research is descriptive frequency distribution method, which is an analysis method by collecting data systematically, analyzing and interpreting data through direct field observation images so as to get conclusions about the current conditions regarding the Buntu Munik Airport construction project. The results of this study indicate that this airport development project has a positive impact on the economy in the area around the airport and has a positive impact on tourism in Tana Toraja and North Toraja regencies.

Keywords:- Economic Development, Labor Conditions, and Tourism Conditions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tana Toraja Regency in the regional and national order is a national and international tourist destination, so the development and development of the transportation system is needed to support and support these activities. Other potential economic activities are the plantation sector (especially coffee plants), forestry (timber and rattan) and livestock. In order to support and support these activities, the airport in Tana Toraja needs to be developed. The condition of transportation infrastructure and facilities is still inadequate. Along with the increase in tourism activities, the level of mobility of tourist visits or the Toraja people themselves is also increasing. One of the increasing mobility

in this transportation field is the trip from Makassar to Tana Toraja or vice versa. From this condition, the local government in synergy with the central government seeks to improve transportation facilities in this case the improvement of the airport. The improvement of air transportation is an effort to build a new airport or develop an old airport. The construction of a new airport (Buntukunik Airport), of course, requires an economic study, both in terms of financing and the expected economic value. So that large investments in infrastructure can be directly proportional to the improvement of the welfare of the Toraja people.

The feasibility analysis of an investment provides an indication of whether the revenue or benefits (benefits) obtained can cover the costs (costs) incurred during the period under review. If the benefits obtained can cover the costs incurred, then the investment is said to be feasible. If the opposite happens, the investment is said to be unfeasible and needs to be reviewed. In the economic feasibility analysis, the benefit review is the benefit obtained by the general public or public in Toraja Regency in an area as a result of the investment made. In this case, the owner or perpetrator of the investment is the public, more specifically the Toraja community. While in the financial feasibility analysis the benefit review is only the revenue obtained in the management of the investment. Of course, if there is no economic feasibility study conducted, it will have an impact on the community and can make the airport become a loss (deserted). The calculation of benefits and costs is the difference between the situation with the project and the situation without the project. The term is used to distinguish the concept of before project and after project.

The investment decision requires an assessment of the future situation that must be planned carefully. In addition, investment decisions are also influenced by future uncertainties caused by technological advances, economic and social changes, changes in government policies and regulations, competition and so on. For this reason, a project feasibility study is needed which aims to evaluate the investment plan by expanding the parking lot, so as to save costs and minimize losses that may arise due to investing

enough bear capital in a less profitable project. Due to the vast aspects of the construction of Buntukunik Airport, this research will only discuss the construction of Buntukunik airport and analyze the economic feasibility study.

Based on the above conditions, the plan to build a new airport in the Tana Toraja Regency area is very important in order to provide faster, effective, efficient and better transportation services to and from the region both to investors, tourism actors, and to improve services to the surrounding community. In order to realize the expectations of the availability of an airport that suits current needs and anticipates future developments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Development Theory*

Development is a process of change that includes all social systems, such as politics, economy, infrastructure, defense, education and technology, institutions, and culture (Alexander 1994). Portes (1976) defines development as economic, social and cultural transformation. Development is a process of planned change to improve various aspects of people's lives.

According to Kumba Digdowiseiso (2019) Transformation in the economic structure, for example, can be seen through an increase or rapid production growth in the industrial and service sectors, so that their contribution to national income is getting bigger. In contrast, the contribution of the agricultural sector will become smaller and inversely proportional to the growth of industrialization and economic modernization. Social transformation can be seen through the distribution of prosperity through equitable access to socioeconomic resources, such as education, health, housing, clean water, recreational facilities, and participation in political decision-making processes. Meanwhile, cultural transformation is often associated, among others, with the rise of the spirit of nationalism and nationalism, in addition to changes in the values and norms adopted by society, such as changes and spiritualism to materialism/secularism. The shift from high valuation to material mastery, from traditional institutions to modern and rational organizations.

➤ *Investment*

The term investment comes from the word investment which in a general sense can be interpreted as "planting" both in the fields of science, engineering, labor, equipment, land, buildings, plants, capital, and so on. While specifically, we mean as capital investment, whether in securities, shares or in working capital or also establishing a company.

The Harrod-Domar theory is one of the theories that continues to be used and developed. This theory was coined by Evsey Domar and Roy Harrod, who worked separately but came to the same conclusion that economic growth is determined by high savings and investment. If public savings and investment are low, then the economic growth of the community or country is also low (Ferry Setiawan, 2019). This can be found in developed and developing countries, people in developed countries are people who have high

investments that are realized in stocks, mutual funds, indices, and other forms of investment. The closest example can be seen how Singaporeans have a high level of investment compared to countries in Southeast Asia. The underlying assumption of this theory is that the problem of development is basically a problem of capital investment. If the investment model is well developed, then the country's economic development will also develop well. So, one of the implications in development in Indonesia, the government encourages investment and things make investment flourish in Indonesia.

➤ *Infrastructure*

One of the components of public services carried out by the government is the provision of infrastructure. The implementation of public services in the form of infrastructure has an influence on the welfare of the people in a region. With good infrastructure, the economic growth of the region will be easier to grow and develop. In addition, good quality infrastructure will also improve the quality of life of the community through improved environmental quality. Furthermore, the existence of infrastructure will encourage an increase in productivity for production factors and vice versa if neglected will reduce productivity (Barus, 2009).

According to Rizky Kurniasih (2019) Infrastructure & Facility Asset Management (MAIF) is a program or knowledge to manage, an infrastructure so that it can continue to carry out its functions well continuously as long as it is still needed, economically, efficiently, and effectively and meets the principles of green or sustainability. Infrastructure asset management must be based on a good knowledge of the characteristics of the infrastructure being managed or discussed. Infrastructure characteristics can be very different from one another. Important characteristics of infrastructure that must be well recognized include: type, class, function, structure, economy, life cycle, operation, maintenance, removal. The goal of infrastructure asset management is to meet the required level of service, in the most effective way, through asset management for current and future customers (Soemitro & Suprayitno, 2018; Suprayitno & Soemitro, 2018; Suprayitno & Soemitro, 2019).

➤ *Development Economics*

Development economics is a branch of economics that studies the economic aspects of the development process in low-income countries. The focus of development economics is not only on methods of increasing economic growth and structural change but also on potential improvements for the population at large, for example, through health and education and improved working environment conditions, both through public and private channels. (Witjaksono, 2006:9).

According to (Mahyudi, 2004: 1) Economic development is economic growth that can cause changes, especially changes in the decline in population growth rates and changes in the structure of the economy, both its role in the formation of national income, as well as its role in providing employment. Economic development focuses

more on efforts to increase people's per capita income on GDP (gross domestic product) accompanied by the overhaul and modernization of the economic sectors and pay attention to aspects of income equity (income equity) while economic growth is more on efforts to increase GDP and regardless of whether the increase is greater or smaller than population growth and regardless of whether there are changes in the economic structure or not.

III. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study was to determine the economic impact of the community around the airport on the Buntu Kunik Airport development project after the airport development project, to determine the impact of labor conditions on the community around the Buntu Kunik Airport after the airport development project and the third to determine the impact of tourism conditions around the Buntu Kunik Airport after development. In this study, researchers used qualitative research to be able to understand phenomena in a natural social context that describes social problems in a person from a behavioral point of view. The location of this research was carried out at Buntukunik Airport, Tana Toraja Regency, South Sulawesi Province. The sample selected in this study amounted to 20 people. The data used for this study include primary data and secondary data. The analysis method used in this research is descriptive frequency distribution method, which is an analysis method by collecting data systematically, analyzing and interpreting data through direct field observation images so as to get conclusions about the current conditions regarding the Buntu Munik Airport construction project.

Fig 1 Components in Data Analysis (Interactive Model)

IV. RESULT

A. Description of Research Results

The impacts of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project will be discussed section by section. These sections include the EIA, perceptions of villagers in the vicinity of the airport towards the Buntu Kunik Airport development project, information on employment opportunities, income levels, land ownership.

➤ Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) in the Area Around the Airport

According to Anwar Muda (2016) There are several alternatives to avoid or overcome environmental impacts at the construction stage such as prevention of erosion,

landslides and dust, which have been made into work procedures that must be carried out by each activity implementer. The Buntu Kunik Airport Development Project is expected to have significant impacts on the environment. These impacts occur in the physical, chemical, biological and socio-cultural environments. The estimation of the magnitude of the impact is carried out by analyzing the AMDAL from the UPT DG Hubud with researcher observations in the field of environmental quality conditions predicted by the existence of businesses and / or activities, and environmental quality conditions predicted without businesses and / or activities.

- *Pre-Construction Stage*

At the pre-construction stage, the hypothetical impact that will be studied further is the impact of community unrest caused by the acquisition and socialization of the activity plan.

- *Community Unrest, Socialization of Activity Plans and Land Acquisition*

Formal or official socialization conducted by the Toraja Regency Government is the initial stage of delivering information to residents of the airport development area with the aim that development runs smoothly and can be well received by residents to residents of the Buntu Kunik airport development area. This official socialization is carried out face-to-face with residents directly.

The results of interviews that have been conducted by researchers together with one of the staff at the Transportation Agency are as follows:

"Project socialization activities are carried out with the aim of providing clear information about the activities to be carried out and to obtain input suggestions and responses from affected communities related to activity plans and prioritize the principle of kinship and deliberation". (interview dated December 05, 2022).

This was confirmed by the Buntu Kunik airport manager and the community who became informants in this study who were also communities around the airport construction.

"This program has indeed conducted socialization in advance before carrying out construction." "Community: the construction of the Toraja airport has long been planned and the local and even central government has often provided socialization about the importance of the construction of the airport." (interview dated January 02, 2023 and January 03, 2023).

- *Construction Phase*

At the construction stage, the hypothetical impacts that will be studied are the impacts of creating employment opportunities, creating business opportunities, increasing income, increasing domestic liquid waste, decreasing air quality, disrupting land traffic, increasing runoff water.

➤ *Creation of Employment Opportunities*

With the new airport construction project in Toraja Regency, employment opportunities are created in the affected communities, so that the UPT Directorate General of Hubud socializes to the community the labor recruitment plan related to the classification of labor needs through electronic media, print media or others. Then inform the schedule and time for implementing labor recruitment activities and provide clear information regarding work contracts and length of work. This is evidenced by the results of an interview with the manager or person in charge of the airport project who said that: "It is true that the construction of the Buntu Kunik airport is expected to have a very large impact on the community, especially on the community around the airport project, and the management has provided information regarding the recruitment of new workers for residents around the Buntu Kunik airport in the hope that the community will not feel that this project is only for workers from outside the area."

This is in line with the results of interviews that have been conducted with people who feel the direct impact of the construction of the Buntu Kunik airport, namely: "There are several positive things that can be felt by residents as a positive impact of the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport. First, some residents are like new rich people (OKB). By receiving compensation money (which is actually compensation for profit), these residents get quite a lot of money. Some residents affected by the relocation policy bought land and built houses in the relocation site, others bought land in another location and then built it, and some bought houses directly. Although they have less money to buy a house, they still have savings for investment, with the saving of the Buntuk Kunik airport it can create business opportunities, especially for MSMEs that do not require large capital so that they can also attract new workers. Thus, the impact of the existence of the Buntuk Kunik airport is that the existence of this airport can improve the economic life of the surrounding community if it can be utilized properly, land prices rise so that residents get significant benefits."

➤ *Creation of Business Opportunities and Increased Income*

With this development project, it will have an impact on the community's economy by doing business or selling around the development project area and will increase the income of the local community. Therefore, the UPT Directorate General of Hubud carries out monitoring directions by collecting data and reporting on activities carried out in the development project area. Researchers conducted field surveys since August-November 2022.

Based on the results of interviews with people who are around the Buntu Kunik airport "With this development project, the community can open a business sector, namely by selling or trading, one of the businesses that can be developed is a souvenir shop, then this development will increase tourism activities in Toraja Regency" (interview dated January 05, 2023).

Based on the results of interviews with Tourism Object Managers who feel the impact of the construction of the Buntu Kunik airport, namely:

"Wellhh, we feel that the construction of this airport will increase the tourism sector because so far many tourists have complained about transportation to Toraja including far because they have to travel 310 Km, the presence of Buntu Kunik Airport is a transportation facility and infrastructure that is expected to increase tourist visits in Toraja and in North Toraja which is famous for having famous traditional tourism."

➤ *Airport Activity Disruption*

Mobilization and demobilization of materials and equipment through two transportation routes, namely mobilization of construction materials and tools carried out by land. This tool and material procurement activity takes place during the construction period. The mobilization and demobilization of heavy equipment and materials by land will cause an increase in exhaust emissions and local dust along the route traveled, predicted to spread to the surrounding environment. These activities have the potential to cause impacts on local air quality degradation caused by vehicle exhaust emissions (CO, NO₂ and SO₂). Increased domestic liquid waste is generated from base camp construction activities. The waste comes from workers who are carrying out project work activities. Based on the results of an interview with the Toraya Indigenous Peoples Alliance (AMAN Toraya), namely: "It is true that the air quality in the construction project area has a lot of dust that can cause public discomfort and channels must be made from waste water to the river run or discharge, this hopefully can be reduced because Toraja is known for its clean natural tourism." (interview dated January 06, 2023).

In maintaining the balance of ecosystems and environmental quality, the South Sulawesi Provincial Government (Sulsel) continues to reforest. Such as in the area of the entrance road to Buntu Kunik Toraja Airport.

• *Operation Stage*

✓ *Increased Noise and Solid Waste*

With this development project increases noise around the local community, it certainly cannot be avoided because the sound of an aircraft has a loud volume, then UPT Ditjen Hubud conducts monitoring directions by reducing the use of equipment that has great potential to cause noise, regulating the schedule of operational activities of machines that have the potential to cause noise, cooperating with local governments in the application of Noise Area Limits. Increased domestic solid waste is generated from airport construction project activities. Waste that comes from the workforce that is doing project work activities. UPT Ditjen Hubud conducts monitoring directions by providing cleaning personnel in the airport area to be free of garbage, coordinating with airplane crews related to garbage from aircraft (ground handling), providing trash bins throughout the Toraja Regency Airport area and collecting data and reporting on this solid waste. Based on the results of

interviews with the community, namely: "There is still a lot of solid waste piled up in the construction project area so that it disturbs the comfort of the community, but not too much because the Toraja Airport operation has not been operating for long". (interview dated January 06, 2023).

✓ *Community Perceptions of the Toraja Airport (Buntu Kunik) Development Project*

Community perceptions regarding the impact of the Toraja Airport (Buntu Kunik) development project in Toraja Regency, can be explained through table 1 below:

Table 1 Distribution of Informant Answers on the Perception of the Impact of the Buntu Kunik Toraja Airport Development Project.

No	Question	Answer Options	Frequency
1	What do you think about the role of the Buntu kunik Airport development project in the economic development of Toraja Regency?	Very instrumental, Buntu kunik Airport will stimulate the growth of Toraja Regency both from the tourism and economic sectors.	26.00
		Buntu Kunik Airport plays a role, slightly improving the economy of Toraja regency	66.00
		Lacking a role, Buntu kunik Airport will not affect the development of Toraja Regency.	6.00
		Not playing a role, Buntu kunik Airport will result in losses for Toraja Regency.	2.00
2	How do you respond to the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project?	A. Strongly agree	30%
		B. Agree	54%
		C. Disagree less	11%
		D. Disagree	5%
	How do you think the future of Buntu Kunik Airport will change after this airport development project?	A. Very good and will grow rapidly	28%
		B. Good and will grow	59%
		C. Poor and difficult to develop	10%
		D. Not good and will not grow	3%
4	How does the ongoing Buntu Kunik Airport development project affect the daily lives of Toraja people?	A. Very annoying	27%
		B. Annoying	30%
		C. Annoying Less	35%
		D. Not Annoying	8%

Source: Research Data (2023)

In question number one, the explanation of informants' answers to the question of the role of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project in the development of Toraja Regency is known as many as 26 people (28%) stated that it played a very important role, 66 people (64%) stated that it played a role where this had the highest point because Buntu Kunik Airport has only been operating for the last 2 years so that economic improvement has not yet been felt, then there is also the pandemic factor which is still slowly recovering, 6 people (6%) stated that it played a lesser role, 2 people (2%) stated that it did not play a role. Thus the majority of informants assessed the role of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project in improving the economy of Toraja Regency from the tourism and economic sectors.

In question number two, the explanation of informants' answers to the question of the response of the Toraja Regency community to the Buntu Kunik Airport development project is known as many as 40 people (40%) stated strongly agree, 50 people (50%) stated agree, 5 people (5%) stated disagree, 5 people (5%) stated disagree. Thus the majority of informants rated agree to the Buntu Kunik Airport development project.

In question number three, the explanation of informants' answers to the question of the responses of the people of Toraja urung Regency about the future changes of Buntu Kunik Airport is known as many as 28 people (28%) stated very good, 59 people (59%) stated good, 10 people (10%) stated less good, 3 people (3%) stated not good. Thus the majority of informants rated good for future changes to Buntu Kunik Airport which is better and developing and will become a potential growth center in the future.

In question number four, the explanation of informants' answers to the question of how the influence of the ongoing Buntu Kunik Airport development project process on the daily lives of residents is known as many as 27 people (27%) stated that it was very disturbing, 30 people (30%) stated that it was disturbing, 35 people (35%) stated that it was less disturbing, 8 people (8%) stated that it was not disturbing. Thus, the majority of informants considered the influence of the ongoing Buntu Kunik Airport development project process to be less disruptive to the daily lives of the people of Toraja Regency.

✓ *Income Levels of Communities Around the Buntu Kunik Airport Development Area*

The income level of the community around Buntu Kunik Airport can be explained in the table below:

Table 2 Distribution of Informant Answers on Income Levels in Toraja Regency Communities Before the Buntu Kunik Airport Development Project

Total Income (Rp)	Number of Informants	Persentase
0-1.000.000	21	22%
1.000.000- 2.000.000	29	29%
2.000.000-3.000.000	27	27%
3.000.000- 4.000.000	10	10%
>5.000.000	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Source: Research Data (Processed) 2023

Table 3 Distribution of Informants' Answers on Income Levels in the Rawa Burung Village Community after the Buntu Kunik Airport Development Project.

Total Income (Rp)	Number of Informants	Persentase
0-1.000.000	15	15%
1.000.000-2.000.000	18	18%
2.000.000-3.000.000	22	22%
3.000.000-4.000.000	34	34%
>5.000.000	11	11%

Source: Research Data (Processed) 2023

Fig 2 The Income of Sebelum and Sesudah

From Figure 2, it is known that the income of informants after the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project has increased. The income of the majority of informants is highest at Rp. 3,000,000-4,000,000 with 34% of informants which before the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project was only 10% of informants. This is because the community around the Buntu Kunik Airport development switched to a better job than before the Buntu Kunik Airport development project. This is in line with Tatan Sukwika (2018) who states that good infrastructure development will also stimulate an increase in the income of the surrounding community, because economic activity is increasing as a result of the mobility of production factors and higher trade activities.

Followed by an income of Rp.0-1,000,000 before the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project only 22% of informants decreased to 15% after the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project. Income of Rp.1,000,000-2,000,000 before the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project was only 27%, which decreased to 18% after the Soekarno-Hatta

International Airport construction project (runway 3). Income of Rp. 2,000,000-3,000,000 before the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project was only 27%, which dropped to 22% after the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project. This decrease in income is because Buntu Kunik Airport has not been operating for long so the direct impact of the development is still in process, but the government claims that the construction of this airport will have a positive impact on the economy of the community around the airport and tourism in Tana Toraja and North Toraja Regency.

Income >5,000,000 before the Buntu Kunik Airport development project was only 7%, increasing to 11% after the Buntu Kunik Airport development project.

✓ *Information on Employment Opportunities to the Community in the Area around the Buntu Kunik airport development*

The answers of community informants in the area around the Buntu Kunik airport development to information on employment opportunities offered by UPT Ditjen Hubud:

Table 4 Distribution of Informant Answers on Employment Opportunities Information for the Regional Community around the airport development of the Buntu Kunik Airport Development Project.

No	Question	Answer Options	Frequency
1.	How do you think the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project on employment opportunities within the scope of UPT Ditjen Hubud on the community around the airport?	A. Very impactful B. Impactful C. Less impactful D. No impact	29% 55% 11% 5%
2.	Do you hear or know about job information in the scope of UPT Ditjen Hubud in the community around the airport?	A. Yes B. Don't Know C. No	51% 45% 4%
3.	How big is the absorption of local labor in the communities around the airport by the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project?	A. Very much, many of the workers on the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project are local workers (from villages around the airport). (> 100 people) B. A lot, about half of the workers on the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project are local workers. (15-100 people) C. Less, Few of the workers on the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project are local workers. (5-15 people) D. Not many, Almost none of the workers on the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project are local workers.	25% 65% 10% 0%

Source: Research data (processed) 2023

- Based on table 4 it can be seen that:

In question number one, the explanation of the informant's answer to the question of the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport construction project on the work of the community in the area around the Buntu Kunik airport development, it is known that 29 people (29%) stated that it had a very strong impact, 55 people (55%) stated that it had an impact, 11 people (11%) stated that it had less impact, 5 people (5%) stated that it had no impact. Thus, the majority of informants assessed the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project on the work of the people of Rawa Burung Village as having an impact.

In question number two, an explanation of the informant's answer to the question whether there is hearing/knowing information about the work offered by UPT Ditjen Hubud to the community in the area around the construction of the Buntu Kunik airport, it is known that 51 people (51%) stated that there was, 45 people (45%) stated that they did not know, 4 people (4%) stated that there was none. Thus the majority of informants considered that they knew about the work offered by UPT Ditjen Hubud to the area around the Buntu Kunik airport development.

In question number three, an explanation of the informant's answer to how much the absorption of local community labor around the Buntu Kunik airport development by the Buntu Kunik airport construction project is known as many as 25 people (25%) stated very much, 65 people (65%) stated a lot, 10 people (10%) stated less. Thus the majority of informants considered a lot of absorption of local labor by the Buntu Kunik airport development project.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Purpose of Buntu Kunik Airport Development

According to Rogers (1985), development is a process of social change that has a broadly participatory nature to advance social and material conditions (including greater justice, freedom and other highly valued qualities) for the majority of people through their acquisition of greater control over their environment. The purpose of the airport development is of course to improve the economy of Toraja Regency, one of which is to increase tourist visits to Tana Toraja, the Minister of Transportation (Menhub) is ready to complete the construction of Buntu Kunik Airport in two years. The Minister of Transportation targets Buntu Kunik Airport to be operational by the end of 2019.

"We see Toraja as an extraordinary tourist destination and we know that tourism is a mainstay for the national economy. Therefore, we are committed to completing this (airport construction) in 2019 so that it will be two budget years, namely this year and next year," said the Minister of Transportation Budi after directly reviewing the construction site of Buntu Kunik Airport in Tana Toraja Regency, South Sulawesi. For this reason, the Minister of Transportation said that the Ministry of Transportation has prepared a budget of Rp 500 billion to complete the construction of Buntu Kunik Airport.

The Regional Government certainly participates in the construction of Buntu Kunik Airport by building access roads. In this regard, the Minister of Transportation claimed to have spoken with the Governor of South Sulawesi and the Regent of Tana Toraja.

Based on the results of interviews with the Toraja Regency Transportation Office, namely: "This is the goal to bring services closer to the community, but it seems that the Toraja people do not fully support and there are pros and cons and even become a prolonged polemic." (interview dated January 09, 2023).

In addition to building an airport, the Minister of Transportation also plans to subsidize airplane ticket prices. This is done to attract more local and foreign tourists to visit Tana Toraja.

It is not easy to build Buntu Kunik Airport. This is due to the geographical conditions and soil structure that need special treatment. The Minister of Transportation explained that the runway of Buntu Kunik Airport will be built on three hills where between the three hills a large river must be made. So that way there needs to be soil reinforcement so that the soil does not collapse. Buntu Kunik Airport will have a runway length of 1600 x 30 meters, an apron of 94.5 x 71.5 meters, and a taxiway of 118 x 15 meters. Later the airport apron can accommodate ATR-72 class aircraft.

B. *Economic Impact of Buntu Kunik Airport Development for the People of Toraja Regency*

➤ *Positive Impacts*

Development is carried out to improve living standards, which are often measured by high income and increased productivity. The airport is a center of activity that has an attraction that triggers changes and development of the area around the airport (Kasarda & Lindsay, 2011). Society is a reality in which there is a process of social interaction and there are also patterns of interaction. The relationship between the economy and society, including processes and patterns of interaction, is mutually influential or reciprocal. Society always changes according to the state of its environment between one community group and another there are different changes.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the community, namely: "The existence of the Buntu Kunik airport has a huge impact on the income of the people in Tana Toraja who are directly adjacent to Enrekang Regency. The impact obtained is regarding changes in household income has increased ". (interview dated January 10, 2023).

Although there are still some who remain at the initial income level before the Buntu Kunik Airport. This situation is influenced by the community capturing existing business opportunities due to increasing tourist visits. Based on data from informants that there are several factors that cause an increase in income, including;

- **Employment Factors** The existence of Buntu Kunik Airport has made active and creative residents have new jobs which also have an effect on increasing income, for example making souvenirs that can be sold around the airport location or at other tourist sites that are positively affected by the airport development. Meanwhile,

residents who are less active and creative in dealing with the situation have no effect on income. Social change is the main consequence of the modernization process experienced by a society (Shahab, Rural Sociology, 2013). The modernization process has an impact on an open way of thinking in order to take advantage of opportunities that exist around them. The increase in income is due to people who are able to capture business opportunities well. After the construction of Buntu Kunik Airport, it can reduce the unemployment rate in Tana Toraja and North Toraja Regency.

Especially in areas directly adjacent to the airport area, Buntu Kunik Airport has a permanent job and income every month because it can work in the airport construction process even though it is as manual labor, motorcycle taxi drivers and there are also those who open food stalls, provide lodging, become Tourgates, and others. In a macroeconomic perspective, the per capita income indicator is a measurable part of human welfare, so that it can describe the welfare and prosperity of society.

- **Increasing Tourism Potential** The existence of Buntu Kunik Airport in Tana Toraja Regency is a gift for Tana Toraja Regency and is adjacent to the sister district of North Toraja, the distance of the two districts is 19km and 38km respectively from Buntu Kunik airport. This has spurred the Regional Governments of Tana Toraja and North Toraja Regencies to improve themselves, especially in the tourism sector. According to Arsyad (1999) regional economic development is a process in which local governments and communities manage existing resources and form a partnership pattern between local governments and the private sector to create new jobs and stimulate the development of economic activities in the region.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers with the Tourism Office, namely: "So with the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport, several new tourism in Toraja and North Toraja Regency have emerged in order to attract tourists both from within and outside the country. Some of the leading tourism in Toraja and North Toraja Regency include Lolai (land above the clouds), Pango-Pango, Buntu Burake, Londa, Lemo and many others. In addition to the increasing tourism objects, tourist visitors to Toraja and North Toraja Regency have increased every year". (interview dated January 11, 2023).

The progress of tourist visits to Toraja and North Toraja Regency increases every year, this can have an impact on the economy of the surrounding community, according to Happy Susanto (2020) the existence of airport development can improve the economic life of the surrounding community if it can be utilized properly, but it must be supported by adequate capital funds, for example to create economic businesses. This airport development also has a social impact so that the order of people's lives can change along with the development of the area to become denser, crowded, and more advanced. Since the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport, there are now more tourist attractions in the Toraja and North

Toraja Regency areas which will aim to improve the economy of the community. Although the distribution of potential tourist attractions in Toraja and North Toraja Regency is high, it still needs to be addressed regarding facilities and infrastructure. The increasing number of potential distribution of tourism objects in Toraja and North Toraja Regency shows the development of creativity by the people of Toraja and North Toraja Regency. Budiman (1995:13) reveals that development does not only deal with the production and distribution of material goods but must also create conditions that support humans to feel safe, happy, and able to develop their creativity.

➤ *Negative Impact*

Increased expenditure The construction of Buntu Kunik Airport has an impact on the attitudes and behavior of the community, of course, it also has an impact on expenditure due to the increased income of the affected Toraja and North Toraja districts. Excessive spending is carried out by the

community for education costs, buying tertiary needs such as cars, building boarding houses, building business premises, besides that it is also due to high land prices which have an impact on high land taxes as well. Since the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport, it has resulted in an increase in the wages that must be given to workers equal to the wages of workers at Buntu Kunik Airport. BS revealed that since the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport, the daily wages of workers have reached 80-100 thousand from the initial 50 thousand, and also spending on land tax prices around the Makale and Rantepao areas has greatly increased, this happened because of the high land prices since the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport. This is in line with research conducted by Bagus (2021) which states that there will be a negative impact caused by airport development.

C. *Impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project on land prices in the area around Buntu Kunik Airport*

Table 5 Distribution of Informants' Answers Regarding the Impact of Development Projects on Land Selling Value in the Area around Buntu Kunik Airport.

Question	Answer Questions	Frekuensi
How do you think the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project on land prices in the area around the airport?	Very impactful, the existence of Buntu Kunik Airport will cause land prices to rise dramatically.	30%
	Impact, Buntu Kunik Airport will increase land prices.	65%
	Less impact, Buntu Kunik Airport will not affect land prices	5%
	No impact, Buntu Kunik Airport will cause land prices to fall.	0%

Source: Research data (processed) 2023

Based on table 5, it can be seen that the explanation of the informant's answer on how the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project on land prices in the area around the airport is known as many as 30 people (30%) stated that it had a great impact, 65 people (65%) stated that it had an impact, 5 people (5%) stated that it had less impact. Thus the majority of informants assess the impact of the Buntu Kunik Airport development project on land prices in the area around the airport, this will certainly have an impact on the development of the Toraja region, especially in the tourism sector.

Based on the results of an interview with the Toraya Indigenous Peoples Alliance (AMAN Toraya), namely: the construction of the Buntuk Kunik airport certainly has an impact on the increase in land prices around the airport because landowners feel that it will be a promising business potential. (interview dated January 12, 2023).

This is in line with Stanislaw Bacior (2021) who states that infrastructure development is one of the real signs of technological progress. Many studies state that transportation infrastructure is one of the most important factors of regional development, allowing the creation of new businesses or supporting contacts with other regions.

VI. CONCLUSION

➤ *Based on the Research Results, it can be Concluded that:*

There is an increase in income in the area around Buntu Kunik Airport. This is driven by the growth in the number of businesses around the development project area in the area around the airport and this will increase the potential for increased tourism. The majority of these businesses then become business fields for the community in the area around the airport. The community created a boarding area for employees working at Buntu Kunik Airport and the emergence of people selling and trading around the airport. It cannot be denied that the airport construction project has had a positive impact on the economy in the area around the airport and has had a positive impact on tourism in Tana Toraja and North Toraja.

There is an increase in the configuration of job shifts for people in the area around the Buntu Kunik Airport. Due to the fact that previously the Dearah community around Buntu Kunik Airport worked on an agrarian basis, for example farming gardening, it turned into a tertiary basis, for example becoming an outsorcing employee in the scope of Buntu Kunik Airport, providing employment opportunities for the village community to work in the scope of Buntu Kunik. And the village community utilizes the employment

opportunities provided by UPT Ditjen Hubud.

The community in Rawa Burung Village mostly owns land with self-ownership with <0.5 hectares with the Buntu Kunik Airport development project the community lost their land such as inheritance, rice fields, plantations. And this causes the price of the sale value of land in the area around the airport to increase. Therefore, the area around the airport and UPT DG Hubud discussed the issue of land selling value. Land in Rawa Burung Village, which initially ranged from Rp.500,000-1,000,000 per meter, rose quite significantly. And the average community selling land to be released is around Rp. 2,000,000-3,000,000 per meter to the UPT Directorate General of Hubud. So this development project has a positive impact on the selling price of land in the villages around the airport.

With the Buntu Kunik Airport development project there will be environmental impacts. From the research conducted on all impacts on environmental components in totality, it can be seen that each impact on the project is interrelated and needs to be carried out environmental management. From the results of the study it is also known that the impact on the physical-chemical component will have an impact on the social component. With this approach, all stages and components of the Soekarno Hatta International Airport development project, Tangerang can be carried out properly.

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